

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF THE EFFECT OF COMMERCIAL CATFISH FEEDS ON THE GROWTH AND BODY COMPOSITION OF *Clarias gariepinus*

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Abstract

In recent times African catfish farming have experienced attention from the government, investors and the science community in Nigeria and other countries of the world.. Hundred fingerlings of mean weight 0.93g and mean length were placed into five treatments. The treatments were fed with five commercial catfish feeds namely: Ziglar(for treatment A); Bluecrown(treatment B);Topfeed(treatment C); Biomer(treatment D) and Vital (treatment E). A nine week feed trial was carried out, with the fish stocked at a density of 5fish/m² using four replicates in a randomized block design.The results from growth evaluation showed that treatments fed Biomer(having 120.52g±18.56) and Bluecrown (having 118.72g±17.8) had significantly ($p < 0.05$) higher than Ziglar(108.33±18.43); Topfeed(113.72±18.34) and Vital(117.33±17.82). Treatments fed Topfeed and Vital produced survival rates of 95% and 90% while the others showed 100% survival rates respectively. Physicochemical parameters namely; PH, dissolved Oxygen and temperature were not significantly different ($p > 0.05$) from across the treatments. The Crude protein obtained from the carcass composition of fish fed with Bluecrown and Biomer were found to be 55.7±3.04 and 54.9±2.64 respectively, and was significantly ($p > 0.05$) different than the initial crude protein recorded before the feed trial which was observed to be 49.63±0.73. Ziglar had crude protien of 52.4±1.39; Topfeed had 50.8±0.59 and Vital 50.2±0.29 respectively. The Ash from the carcass before feeding was not significantly ($p > 0.05$) difference from the carcass of the fish fed Biomer (8.6±0.2) , Topfeed(7.5±0.35), and Vital (9.2±0.5). Ziglar (5.2±1.5) and Biomer(6.3±0.95) were significantly ($p < 0.05$) different from the value of ash before feeding. Crude lipid was found to be Ziglar (16.25±0.09); Bluecrown (15.9±0.26); Topfeed (13.6±1.41);Biomer (15.8±0.31) and Vital (16.8±0.19). Crude fat was highest in the fish fed Vital feed. All carcass samples had nitrogen free extract values higher than that of the carcass before feeding except Bluecrown; which was significantly lower than that of the carcass of the fish before feeding. Fibre was highest for the fish fed Topfeed(10.6±2.9)while the least was bluecrown (8.2±1.7). Ziglar, Topfeed and Vital had (8.7±1.95), (7.5±1.35) and (8.8±2.0) respectively which were all significantly higher than the value before feeding (4.8±0.45). These findings support that feed composition affects growth and body composition parameters. Feeds with crude protein content above 44% of the composition is recommended for optimum growth.

Introduction

Catfish (*Clarias* sp.) are the major commercial cultured species in Nigeria for good market culture reasons (Anetekhai et al., 2004). There are many cultivable catfish species which are but not limited to *Clarias gariepinus*, *C. anguillaris*, *Heterobranchus bidorsalis*, *H. longifillis*, *C.*

Isheriensis, *C. submarginatus*, *Chrysichthys nigrodigitatus*, *Bagrus* sp , *Synodontis* Sp. *Clarias gariepinus* is one of the most cultured fish in Nigeria and Africa. *Clarias gariepinus*, despite being native to Africa, has been introduced to other parts of the world including Asia and the Middle East. It has been reported that it is spreading around the world particularly due to the exploitation of aquaculture. (Cambray, 2005).

The *Clarias gariepinus* is a more preferred fish for aquaculture because of its growth rate, good market price, robustness, ease of breeding. This has made it a subject of investigation among several species of fish. *Clarias gariepinus* has been known to have high adaptive functions which support its culture. *C.gariepinus* can adapt to reduced oxygen in water, when they are 14 days old with developed respiratory and accessory respiratory organs.(Ogundiran et al., 2009). *Clarias gariepinus* shows tolerance to temperature variations with little stress. It has been known to have long tolerance for drought and low temperature below 10°C (Abalaka, 2013). *Clarias gariepinus* is reared in ponds and in concrete, fiberglass and plastic tanks with intensifications. Traditional flooded ponds, where naturally recruited fingerlings are gathered during the rainy season and exogenous feed is provided, constitute a form of capture based agriculture. (FAO, 2021).

Since the year 2000 there has been a rapid expansion in urban aquaculture and a significant development in high density catfish aquaculture (Agokei et al., 2010). Fish feed alone accounts for at least 60% of the total cost of fish production (Jamu&Ayinla, 2007), these feeds are imported or locally manufactured. In an attempt to find cheaper, affordable, available alternative fish feed to imported commercial fish feeds, various local fish feeds have been formulated from different varieties of rising local manufacturers. (Ofonime & Gift, 2017).

Fish feed is usually compounded to include basic nutrients for growth and health. The nutritional value of feed stuff in terms of feed formation for cultural fish in particular depends on their digestible crude protein and digestible energy (Dong, 2006). The essential nutrients such as vitamins, protein, fat, carbohydrates and minerals are required for the formation of body tissues, production of energy and also for regulation of physiological processes (Haruna, 2003).

The goal of commercial fish farmers is to possibly get the fingerlings to grow to table size of 1kg weight and above in less than 6 months. Success in the production of fish is a function of the final weight gain and survival rate which in turn is dependent on knowledge in fish production, and the application of the technical management practices acquired by the farmer.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

The research was carried out in the department of biology in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt.

Experimental Fish

A total of 100 similar sized *Clarias gariepinus* fingerlings will be selected and purchased from the same stock spawned at a reputable local farm hatchery. The fingerlings had a mean weight of 0.93g and an initial mean length of 4.45cm. The fish was acclimatized in laboratory for 24 hours before the commencement of the experiment.

Experimental Feed

Five commercial feed namely; Biomer, Vital, Ziglar, Bluecrown and Top feed was sourced from the local market for the experiment. The feeds were sourced in their 1.5mm

granulated size. The feed were designated Zigler (FA), Vital (FE), Biomer (FD), Bluecrown (FB), and Top feed (FC).

3.2 Experimental Design

The 100 fish samples they were stocked in concrete tanks labelled A to E respectively with 4 replicates of plastic tanks for each treatment designated as A2 to A4 respectively for treatment A, and B2, B3.....E4 bringing the total of treatments to 20. The treatments were randomly arranged in the work area using the randomized block design. The fingerlings were stocked at a density of 5 fingerlings per treatment tank. The volume of the pond was 1m x 1m x 1m and borehole water was used to fill the ponds at a depth of 50cm.

The fingerlings were acclimated for 24hours upon their introduction into the ponds to empty their gut and get them ready for the feed experiment. The feeds were arranged to their designated treatments. Zigler (FA) was fed to treatments A, Vital (FE) was fed to treatments E, Biomer (FD) was fed to treatments D, Bluecrown (FB) was fed to treatments B, and Top feed (FC) was fed to treatments C. The experiment area was shielded to prevent unauthorized access and possible predators. The fish were fed ad libitum twice a day. The same weight from different feeds was given to the treatments. The individuals from each was weighed and recorded weekly respectively. Water was changed weekly to reduce the stress; it was done during data collection.

Determination of Growth Performance

The weight of the samples was collected weekly by draining the water from the ponds. The mean weight was obtained after analyzing the weight data from all the samples in each respective pond.

Data collection for length and survival was also collected after weighing the samples.

Data collected was used to calculate the mean weight gain, daily weight gain, relative weight gain, number of survival, condition factor, feed conversion ratio, protein efficiency ratio for every treatment using the following formulae:

Mean weight gain (g) (MWG)

$$MWG = W_{t_2} - W_{t_1}$$

Where W_{t_1} = initial weight of the fish at time T_1

W_{t_2} = final weight of the fish at time T_2

Daily weight gain (g/day) (DWG)

$$(DWG) = \frac{\text{Final weight} - \text{Initial mean weight}}{\text{Rearing period in days}}$$

Specific growth rate (%day)

$$\frac{\text{Final body weight (g)} - \text{Initial bodyweight (g)}}{\text{Culture days} \times 100}$$

$$\text{Condition Factor (K)} = \frac{\text{Body Weight (g)} \times 100}{\text{Body Length (cm)}}$$

$$\text{Feed Conversion Ratio} = \frac{\text{Feed given (g)}}{\text{Weight gain (g)}}$$

$$\text{Protein Efficiency Ratio} = \frac{\text{Weight gain (g)}}{\text{Protein Intake (g)}}$$

$$\text{Survival Rate (\%)} = \frac{\text{Number of Fish Harvested}}{\text{Number of Fish Stocked}} \times 100$$

Proximate analysis

The fish samples were sacrificed and cleaned for the proximate analysis. The proximate compositions were carried out in order as described by AOAC (2000). The analysis of each treatment was carried out in duplicates.

Results

Proximate analysis of experimental diets

The proximate analysis of the feed used in this study can be found in table. Feed D and A, are commercial manufactured feeds while B, C and E were locally manufactured feeds. The range for crude protein content in the composition of the experimental feeds was between the ranges of 49%-42%. Feed D had the highest protein content in its composition while feed E had the lowest. Fat content was within the range of 10-12%, with Feed s A, D and E having 12% and feeds C and B having 10% each. Crude fiber was within the range of 2-7%.

Table 4.1: Proximate Composition of Experimental Feed

Parameters	Feed (Ziglar)	A Feed (Bluecrown)	B Feed (Topfeed)	C Feed (Biomer)	D Feed (Vital)	E
Crude protein (%)	44	45	45	49	42	
Fat (%)	12	10	10	12	12	
Crude fiber (%)	2	4.5	7	4.2	5.5	
Phosphorus (%)	1	1.5	2.4	1.13	1.8	
Sodium (%)	0.5	0.30	1.4	0.24	0.8	
Ash (%)	5	8	7	6	10	
Moisture content (%)	7.5	6.8	8.3	7.4	7.7	

Physicochemical properties

The value for the dissolved Oxygen for all the treatments showed no significant (p 0.05) difference. The range for the individual treatments are; A (6.2 – 7.65), B (6.60 – 7.20), C (6.83 – 7.32), D (6.58 – 7.56) and E (6.68 – 7.42). As can be seen in table 2. The cumulative range for dissolved oxygen was 6.21 – 7.65. The cumulative PH range of this study was from 6.04 – 7.54, as presented in Table4.1. The highest PH was found in treatment B while the lowest was found in treatment E. The cumulative range of temperature for the experiment was between 24.60°C – 26.30 °C, the highest values were found in treatments A and C, and the least was found in treatment C.

Table 4.2: Physicochemical conditions

Parameters	ziglar Treatment	Bluecrown Treatment	Topfeed Treatment	Biomer Treatment	Vital Treatment
Dissolved oxygen	7.09±0.24	6.9 ± 0.11	7.13 ±0.09	7.14 ± 0.18	7.12 ± 0.14
PH	6.81±0.16	7.06 ± 0.16	6.83 ± 0.14	6.90 ±0.08	6.56 ± 0.25
Temperature	25.55±0.24	24.84 ±0.36	25.67 ±0.24	25.29 ±0.25	24.80 ±0.33

Table 4.3: Growth parameters of treatments fed with different feeds

Parameter s	Treatment A	Treatment B	Treatment C	Treatment D	Treatment E
Daily weight gain (g/day)	0.32±0.012 ^a	0.35±0.024 ^a	0.31±0.072 ^b	0.37±0.031 ^a	0.33±0.015 ^a
Specific Growth Rate (g/day %)	0.065±0.18 ^a	0.070±0.016 ^a	0.061±0.014 ^a	0.075±0.017 ^a	0.059±0.014 ^b
Condition factor	161.05±1.22a	151.32±1.06b	142.21±1.14c	162.26±1.45a	147.11±1.49b
Feed conversion Ratio	51.70±5.09 ^a	47.95±5.02 ^b	54.46±5.1 ^a	44.55±5.3 ^c	50.41±5.05 ^b
Protein Efficiency Ratio	0.044±0.012 ^a	0.046±0.043 ^b	0.041±0.021 ^a	0.046±0.017 ^b	0.047±0.019 ^b
Gross total weight	2157.16±38.16 ^a	2374.04±39.63 ^b	1874.39±06 ^c	2407.33±38.3 ^b	2226.66±37.3 ^a
Mean weight	108.33±18.43 ^a	118.72±17.8	113.72±18.34 ^a	120.52±18.56	117.33±17.82
Gross total length	1940.6±34.76	2186.1±32.8	2197.4±35.7	2229.3±33.9	2102±34.5
Mean length	101.35±17.8 ^a	109.47±16.8	109.92±18.3	111.23±18.6	109.93±18.3
Weight gain	20.31±0.95	21.9±0.86	19.28±0.83 ^a	23.57±0.92	20.83±0.76
Length gain	7.97±0.51 ^a	10.42±0.48	9.73±0.63	10.66±0.75	10.66±0.65
Survival rate%	100	100	95	100	90

Note: Means across the rows bearing same superscript are not different significantly (P<0.05)

Proximate analysis of *Clarias gariepinus* before and after feeding treatment

Table 4.4. The result of the proximate composition of the fish carcass before and after feed trials

Composition %	Initial carcass X	Carcass from Ziglar Treatment	Carcass from Bluecrown Treatment	Carcass from Topfeed Treatment	Carcass from Biomer Treatment	Carcass from Vital Treatment
Crude Protein	49.63 ± 0.79 ^a	52.4 ± 1.39 ^a	55.7 ± 3.04 ^b	50.8 ± 0.59 ^a	54.9 ± 2.64 ^b	50.2 ± 0.29 ^a
Ash	8.2 ± 0.75 ^a	5.2 ± 1.5 ^b	8.6 ± 0.2 ^a	7.5 ± 0.35 ^a	6.3 ± 0.95 ^b	9.2 ± 0.5 ^a
Nitrogen Free Extract	6.75 ± 0.41 ^a	7.2 ± 0.24 ^b	6.5 ± 0.11 ^a	7.5 ± 0.39 ^c	7.8 ± 0.54 ^c	7.2 ± 0.24 ^b
Crude Lipid	16.42 ± 0.22 ^a	16.25 ± 0.09 ^a	15.9 ± 0.26 ^a	13.6 ± 1.41 ^b	15.8 ± 0.31 ^b	16.8 ± 0.19 ^a
Crude Fiber	4.8 ± 0.45 ^a	8.7 ± 1.95 ^b	8.2 ± 1.7 ^b	10.6 ± 2.9 ^c	7.5 ± 1.35 ^b	8.8 ± 2.0 ^b

Note: means across the rows bearing same superscript are not different significantly (P<0.05)

All treatments exceeded the crude protein level recorded in the carcass of the initial fish before feeding. The higher recorded value for crude protein was found in treatment B and D, 55.7% and 54.9% respectively, while the lesser values were recorded for treatments A, C and E having values of 52.4%, 50.8% and 50.2% respectively. The value of the crude protein for treatments A, B and D was significantly different (P<0.05) and was higher than the initial carcass crude protein. Treatments C and E were similar and showed no significant difference (P<0.05) with the initial carcass.

The initial fish had an ash content of 8.2% upon analysis. The treatments recorded ash concentrations 5.2%, 8.6%, 7.5%, 6.3%, and 9.2% for treatments A to E respectively. The ash contents for treatments A, D and C were significantly different (P<0.05) from that of the initial

carcass composition. Treatments B and E showed no significant difference ($P > 0.05$) from the initial carcass composition. Treatments A and D were significantly similar ($P > 0.05$).

Nitrogen free extract (NFE) was found to be 6.75% of the initial fish carcass before feeding trial. Treatments A to E had values of NFE as 7.2%, 6.5%, 7.5%, 7.8%, and 7.2% respectively. The Nitrogen free extracts for treatments B and D were significantly different ($P < 0.05$) from the initial carcass composition, while treatments A, C and E were significantly similar ($P > 0.05$) to the NFE of the initial carcass composition.

Crude lipid was found to be 16.25%, 15.9%, 13.6%, 15.8%, and 16.8% for treatments A to E respectively as against the value of crude lipid analysed in the fish before feeding and found to be 16.42%. Crude lipid in treatments A, B and E was significantly similar ($p > 0.05$) with the initial fish carcass, while treatments C and D showed significant ($P < 0.05$) difference.

Crude fiber was found to be 4.8% in the initial carcass composition of the fish before the feeding trial. After the trial the value of crude fiber from the carcass compositions of the treatments were 8.7%, 8.2%, 10.6%, 7.5%, and 8.8% for treatments A to E respectively. Crude fiber for all the treatments was significantly different ($P < 0.05$) in all the treatments against the initial fish crude fiber value.

Discussion

The result from the proximate analysis showed that the feeds used for Treatments D, B and A, had higher proportion of crude lipids to fiber content. These treatments showed greater mean growth and feed conversion rate than the rest in the study. This is in agreement with the study of Orire et al., (2013) which reported that the feeds in their study with higher lipid than fiber content produced the highest mean growth rate recorded as well as the greatest feed conversion rate from the experiment.

The feeds used in this study possessing lesser fiber content in the composition namely; feeds A(2%), D(4.2%) and B(4.5%), performed most favorably in terms of weight gain and mean growth rate than the feeds with higher fiber content; C(7%) and E(5.5%). This observation is in agreement of the findings of Adebayo et al ., (2020) which stated that the treatments in their study, fed with feeds containing lesser amounts of fiber showed higher mean growth rates and feed conversion rate. These findings may be due to the fact that fiber is not easily digestible by the digestive system of *C. gariepinus*, therefore a composition of feed with high levels of fiber will be slowly and incompletely digested by the fish.

The treatments in this study fed with foreign manufactured commercial feeds namely; A(Ziglar) and D(Biomer) were found to produce significantly higher specific growth rate and feed conversion rates than the locally manufactured commercial feeds; B(Bluecrown), C(Topfeed) and E(Vital). Feed A had a feed conversion rate value of 51.70 ± 19.44 while feed D had a feed conversion rate of 54.46 ± 19.44 . This was supported by the report of Awotoye and Adesina (2020) which concluded that a foreign feed named Skretting yielded more mean growth and feed conversion rate than Bluecrown a locally manufactured viable feed. The variations of the results may be due to the composition and the ingredients used in the formulation by the manufacturing companies. Moshood et al.,(2014) corroborated with the findings of this study. They observed that some local feeds faired significantly lower than foreign feeds used in their study. They also found that the feed conversion ratio was lesser than that of the foreign feeds.

The treatments D having 49% protein in composition and A and having 44% content in composition, effected the highest recorded mean weight gain and mean length gain in the experiment. This also indicated the higher values of protein efficiency rate found in treatments B, D and E. The rest of the feeds created significant weight and length gain. Remarkably the feed given to treatment C with 45% protein composition did not significantly create much weight gain

and length as treatment D and treatment E. High protein content is essential since *Clarias gariepinus* is carnivorous and requires high protein for growth and stability. The observation of this study is in correlation with the findings of Nabulime M. et al., (2015) which recorded that the mean growth rate was highest for its feed sample with a protein composition of 60%.

The result showed that treatment feed with high protein and fat content equal to or below 12% of the composition showed greater mean weight and specific growth rates correspondingly. This finding is in concordance with the report of Abalaka and Sotolu , (2012) which evaluated the use of chicken parts unfit for human consumption as feed protein and fat ingredient , resulting in lipid content above 13% and above. The report stated that there was a reduction in growth rate in comparison with the control and also an increase in mortality.

Treatments A, B and D recorded 100% survival rate, while treatments C and E recorded 95% and 90% survival rates respectively. This results showing higher survival rate generally could be attributed to the low stocking density of five fingerlings per tank. The resulting losses could however be due to stress due to changing of water or feeding culture. The resulting high survival rate could also be caused by the favorable physicochemical condition of the environment. The findings of Omeru et al., (2016) reported that physiochemical conditions can increase survival rates in fish.

The fish composition of the treatments recorded crude protein values higher than that of the initial fish before feeding trial which was 49.63% of the body composition. This is due to feed utilization and growth. This was also observed by Sotolu and Faturoti (2009) and Orire et al.,(2016). The highest values for crude proteins in body compositions were found in the samples

from B and D, 55.7% and 54.9% respectively. This is due to the fact that the feeds used in B and D had the highest recorded crude proteins in the proximate analysis of the feeds.

The ash content of samples from B and E was significantly higher than the initial ash content before feeding. This is majorly due to the fact that is more minerals in the fish and the ingredients used in the formulation of the feed. The values of Ash from the feeds given to B and E from the proximate analysis of the feeds used in the treatments were observed to be higher in comparison to other feeds. The values of ash against the initial composition was in relation to those observed by Sotolu aand Faturoti, (2009) which also observed differing values across the feeding trials. The values however were also in concordance of the results from Ofonime and Edet, (2017) which showed that there was a slight increase in Ash content between the *C. gariepinus* before feeding and the *C. gariepinus* after the feeding.

Nitrogen free extract was higher in the body compositions of the fed *C. gariepinus* except in treatment B which was found to be lower than that of the initial *C. gariepinus* value. Treatments A , C and E had NFE significantly similar ($P>0.05$) with the initial *C. gariepinus*. The differing values of the treatments could be due to the different composition and different ingredient used in their feed composition. The results in this experiment were not in concordance with the results observed in Ibidumi et al , (2017) and Abalaka and Saidu, (2012).Crude lipid was significantly similar($P>0.05$) between treatments A, B , E and the initial *C. gariepinus*. Treatment E had the highest value which was the only value higher than the initial composition. The feeds used for A, D and E had the highest value of crude fat in their compositions which was 12% for each of them. This may be the reason for the observed increase in crude fat above the rest treatments. Excess fat could be debilitating to the liver of *C. gariepinus*. The crude fiber contents for the treatments were significantly different ($P<0.05$) and higher than the crude fiber content of the initial carcass of the *C. gariepinus* sample. The highest values were recorded for

C and the lowest for D. This is due to the fact that crude fiber in the feed given to treatment A was 7% of the feed composition and was the highest across the treatments. There is an obvious absorption of fiber from the feed over time. Treatment D and A had lesser values for crude fiber because their feed also had lesser values of crude fiber in their compositions respectively.

Conclusion

From the findings of this research we can be able to deduce that the composition of the feeds affects the growth parameters and also the body composition of the fish.

Recommendation

Farmers should collaborate with the science community to improve and innovate commercial catfish feeds utilizing local but potent ingredients in the compositions.

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